

NICKEL ALUMINATE (NiAl_2O_4): AN EFFICIENT CATALYST FOR ORGANIC TRANSFORMATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Nano-sized crystal materials of NiAl_2O_4 metallic doped catalyst has been productively created by sol-gel combustion manner with the proper proportions of glycine supported nickel nitrate, aluminium nitrate and heated under the highest temperature on 900°C performed into the muffle furnace. The structural, morphological and spectral properties have been examined by using FT-IR, EDS and FESEM study exposed the formation of crystalline NiAl_2O_4 Nano-particles. This afforded metals catalyst has been employed as catalyst in the synthesis of different substituted amine derivatives by conventional method. It was found that the highest yield acquired in the synthesis of the N-substituted formamide derivatives by the application of nickel aluminate nano-catalyst.

KEYWORDS: Sol-gel-combustion, nickel aluminate catalyst, Substituted formamides.

INTRODUCTION

Oxide spinels are a large category of compounds of mixed-metal oxides crystallizing into AB_2O_4 kind structure. The nickel aluminate spinel has received attention as a catalyst solid support due to its stability, substantial resistance to acids and alkalis and high melting point [1]. The NiAl_2O_4 nano-material possesses a unique structure consisting of grains, grain limits, surfaces and pores, creating it appropriate to be used as catalyst support once its microstructures are measured [2]. In recent times, the development of NiAl_2O_4 for advanced applications, particularly as a solid support for metal catalysts, has been dispensed. The synthesis of NiAl_2O_4 to be used as nickel catalyst support for the hydro-dechlorogenation of the trichlorobenzene within the gas phase, transformation of nickel or aluminium stratified double hydroxides to nickel or corundum and nickel or nickel aluminate composites that have found utility as methylated catalysts within the treatment of carbon monoxide gas, irritating gases, replacement process material based on the addition of the new binder nickel aluminate and applied it to chemical process combustion, preparation conditions for nickel aluminum hydroxide gels and calcination temperatures on the ultimate structure of the nickel aluminate [3-6]. It is found in various natural products and also one of the most productive moieties in the modern chemical, agricultural, medicinal and pharmaceutical molecules. Formamides are so valuable compound in pharmaceutical industry [7-9]. In pharmaceutical's nitrogen containing compound are require in high demand and formamide are good to protect the nitrogen in amines. It is frequently recognized that the nano-particles with well-ordered size and conformation have been shown the fundamental and scientific importance. The fabrication method decides not only the products appearances such as size and shape, but also their physical properties. Aluminates are commonly manufactured by the ceramic technique which involves high-temperature solid state reactions lined by the oxide constituents [10-13]. One of the important route to prepare aluminates is sol-gel combustion method and here the researchers has been prepared glycine assisted NiAl_2O_4 metal catalyst and tested their catalytic properties in the conversion of substituted amines in conventional heating synthesis.

Synthesis of NiAl₂O₄ Spinel System:

For the synthesis of nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄) spinel frameworks commercially bought synthetic compounds were analytical grade from Merck, India and were utilized without further purification. Aluminum nitrate, Nickel nitrate and Glycine were utilized as the fuel. The samples were set up with the expansion of Ni⁺⁺ of molar proportions. The schematic technique for the readiness of nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄) spinel framework combined by sol-gel combustion strategy appeared by the flow diagram-1;

Diagram-1: Preparation flow diagram of NiAl₂O₄ sample

Experimental procedure for the synthesis of NiAl₂O₄ spinel system:

The nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄) spinel framework was blended by sol-gel combustion strategy. The technique includes wet chemical blending of the calculated proportion of 4.567g of nickel nitrate and 18.75g of aluminum nitrate and 15g glycine were gradually blended with steady mixing till the homogeneous blend with the formation of gel. The subsequent gel was heated on hot plate at 250°C temperature for 15-20 minutes till the development of blackish char. At that point the char was collected in to the vessel and heated up to the 900°C for 2 hours in the muffle furnace which forms greenish-blue coloured nano-particles. These nano-particles were described by the succeeding measures for instance of the stoichiometric molar proportion of the nickel nitrate, aluminum nitrate [14].

Characterization of NiAl₂O₄ Spinel System:

The structural characterization of spinel NiAl₂O₄ sample was performed using a Perkin Elmer FT-IR spectrometer the analysis of surface functional groups. The surface morphology of the samples was achieved at desired magnification with a Joel JSM 6360 field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray (EDS) for elemental composition analysis, reactions were monitored by GCMS, 400 MHz Bruker NMR.

FT-IR of NiAl₂O₄ Spinel System:

The FT-IR spectra of spinel NiAl₂O₄ nanoparticles formed an influential and extensive absorption band detected at around in the region 3448 cm⁻¹ which may be fixed to the vibrations of twofold compound

molecules. A band observed at around 1629 cm⁻¹ is present in total configurations, which might be appointed to the H–O–H bending vibration. FTIR spectrum indicates the characteristics peaks spinal segment at about 715–508 cm⁻¹ that ensures the cubical spinel structure. The detected peak at 508 cm⁻¹ was associated with broadening vibration mode of Al–O for the octahedral coordinated Al³⁺ ions. Overall compositions of NiAl₂O₄ sample, the metal-oxygen (M–O) stretching frequencies are reportable within the range 715 cm⁻¹ to 508 cm⁻¹, connected with the vibrations of Al–O and Ni–O–Al bonds.

Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy analysis:

The chemical compositions of the catalysts determined from the EDS information have been very just like those calculated through making use of the simplest criterion that needs to be fulfilled for you to shape a perovskite-kind shape that is the ionic radii necessity introduced by way of Goldschmidt [15], consequently referred to as tolerance element defined by equation. The common theoretical composition (EDS) has additionally been calculated from the percentage of nickel and vanadium cations inside the B-sites of the perovskite, which turned into varied between $x=0$ for Ni_xAl₂O₄ and $x=zero$ there may be excellent arrangement between the experimental and theoretical (EDS) perovskite compositions for NiAl₂O₄, while the slight distinction in elemental composition is probably because of a difference in stoichiometry with regard to oxygen. EDS analysis confirmed that the homogeneity of the catalyst after the test become just like that before the patterned for $x=zero$, localized parts of better nickel concentrations are designed. It exhibited Ni, Al and O peaks and indicated the presence of NiAl₂O₄ phase. The peaks at 0.5, 0.8 and 1.5 keV in the EDS spectra were due to the oxygen, nickel and aluminium element present in the sample before recording FESEM.

Spectra-1:EDS analysis of NiAl₂O₄ sample

Therefore the elemental analysis of the sample was carried out by using energy dispersive X-ray (EDS) resulting the fractions of elements in the K-series are found the weight of Ni (0.98%), Al (1.28%) and O (4.25) correspondingly. Thus it is clearly displays that the nano-crystalline NiAl₂O₄ comprises only Ni, Al and O without any impurity.

Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESM) analysis:

The Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope analysis of the NiAl₂O₄ synthesized by sol-gel combustion technique, the NiAl₂O₄ sample had a totally distinctive structure and surface morphology. FESM micrograph of the NiAl₂O₄ sample is homogenized and well defined spinel particles of nano-metric in size were proven by FESEM images by the different magnification of a singular NiAl₂O₄ sample. The particle morphology is kind of uniform for each sample suggesting that this technique of synthesis yields a consistent material with uniform particle sizes. The scale and particles were measured for as prepared and NiAl₂O₄ sample severally by the different magnification for different sizes starting from from 50000 magnifications

with 15 kV WD of 4.9 mm spot 3 under the pressure of 1.66e-4 Pa in the SE mode for the particle size 2 μm as shown in the fig-1.

Fig-1: FSEM of 2 μm magnified article size of NiAl₂O₄ sample

Thus it was found that, the most significant particle size distribution was the specific range that was measured somewhat superlative appearances for the mixed metal aluminate spinel systems.

Catalytic study of NiAl₂O₄ nanomaterial:

The applications of the developed nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄) nano-material as a catalyst for the N-formylation of amines to synthesize the substituted formamides were accomplished. All reactions were performed by using the sealing glass tube and the yield were calculated on gas chromatography and products were analyzed by using GCMS.

Material method:

Synthesis of N-phenylformamide:

Aniline (1mmole) and formamide (1mL) was mixed with NiAl₂O₄ (5mg) at solvent free condition and heated under with constant stirring for 15 hours for the conversion of N-ethyl-N-phenylformamide as revealed in the **scheme-1**. The reaction was continuously monitored by GCMS. The molecular formula of the synthesized compounds is C₇H₇NO, Mol. Wt.: 121 m/z, Practical yield: 98%, FTIR (ATR): 1728, 1347, 1463, 1505 and 1634 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO *d*⁶, δ ppm): 7.21-7.51 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 8.6 (s, 1H), obtained yield is 86%.

Scheme-1: Preparation of N-phenylformamides by NiAl₂O₄ catalyst

Synthesis of N-ethyl-N-phenylformamide:

N-ethylbenzamine (1mmole) and formamide (1mL) was mixed with NiAl₂O₄ (5mg) at solvent free state and heated under with continuous stirring for 15 hours for the conversion of N-ethyl-N-phenylformamide as shown in the **scheme-2**. The reaction was constantly monitored by GCMS. The molecular formula of the prepared compounds is C₉H₁₁NO, Mol. Wt.: 149 m/z, Practical yield: 98%, FTIR (ATR): 1719, 1297, 1451, 1518 and 1614 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO *d*⁶, δ ppm): 7.19-7.46 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 1.0 (t, 3H), 8.1 (s),

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